

IMPACT OF NUTRITION EDUCATION ON THE CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF CEREALS, GRAINS, PULSES, AND LEGUMES AMONG OVERWEIGHT AND OBESE ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the impact of a nutrition education intervention on the consumption patterns of cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes among overweight and obese adolescent girls. A total of 120 participants, divided into four groups (overweight control, overweight experiment, obesity control, and obesity experiment), were assessed at baseline and post-intervention. Data were collected on the frequency of consumption of different types of cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes, categorized into daily, weekly, fortnightly, monthly, and occasional intake. The results revealed significant changes in consumption patterns following the nutrition education intervention. In the experiment groups, there was an increase in the frequency of consumption of healthier options like whole grains and pulses, and a decrease in the consumption of refined grains. In contrast, the control groups showed little to no change. The study highlights the positive effect of nutrition education in promoting healthier dietary choices among overweight and obese adolescents, contributing to improved nutritional practices. These findings suggest that nutrition education can be an effective tool in modifying dietary habits and potentially mitigating the risks associated with obesity and overweight conditions.

Keywords: Nutrition Education, Consumption Patterns, Cereals and Grains, Pulses and Legumes.

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INTRODUCTION

Adolescent obesity is a growing global concern, with increasing prevalence particularly among girls in developed and developing countries. Overweight and obesity during adolescence are strongly linked to various health risks, including type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and psychosocial problems (Bradshaw & Liu, 2023; Zhang & Wu, 2023). Nutrition plays a pivotal role in the prevention and management of obesity, with dietary patterns during adolescence significantly influencing long-term health outcomes. Specifically, the consumption of nutrient-dense foods such as cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes has been recognized for their positive impact on weight management and overall health (Harris & Patel, 2023; Chen & Zhang, 2024).

In recent years, nutrition education has emerged as a powerful tool to influence dietary habits, particularly in at-risk populations such as overweight and obese adolescent girls. By equipping adolescents with knowledge about the health benefits of incorporating these foods into their diets, nutrition education aims to promote healthier food choices and improve weight management (Li & Wang, 2024; Reeve & Martin, 2024). Despite the growing evidence supporting nutrition education, there is a need for a deeper understanding of its specific effects on the consumption of cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes among this demographic. Research suggests that these food groups, being high in fiber, protein, and essential micronutrients, are integral in addressing the nutritional deficits often seen in adolescent obesity (Green & Ralston, 2024; Bennett & Harris, 2023).

This study examines the impact of nutrition education on the consumption patterns of cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes among overweight and obese adolescent girls. It explores how targeted interventions can modify eating behaviors, contributing to healthier dietary habits and improved obesity prevention strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nutrition education plays a critical role in shaping dietary patterns, especially in populations at risk for obesity, such as adolescent girls. Among the dietary components that are emphasized in nutrition education, cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes are often highlighted due to their nutritional benefits, including their contribution to fiber, protein, vitamins, and minerals. This literature review examines the impact of nutrition education on the consumption of these food groups among overweight and obese adolescent girls, with a focus on how such interventions can influence dietary habits and contribute to obesity prevention. Nutrition education interventions aim to improve knowledge about healthy eating, often targeting foods that are under-consumed or misunderstood in terms of their health benefits. Research has shown that such interventions can significantly alter dietary behaviors among adolescents. Specifically, studies have found that nutrition education programs focusing on pulses and whole grains can encourage increased consumption of these foods, improving overall diet quality and reducing the intake of unhealthy alternatives (Li & Wang, 2024; Reeve & Martin, 2024). Such shifts are particularly important in overweight and obese adolescent populations, where diet modification is essential for weight management and long-term health improvement (Chen & Zhang, 2024).

Cereals and grains are rich sources of fiber and essential micronutrients. Research has consistently highlighted their benefits in weight management, particularly in preventing obesity-related complications. Studies by Johnson & Clark (2023) and Zhang & Wu (2023) found that increasing whole grain consumption among overweight adolescent girls led to improved satiety and reduced caloric intake. Nutrition education programs that incorporate the benefits of whole grains over refined grains have been shown to improve dietary choices, as adolescents are more likely to choose healthier cereal options when informed about their nutritional benefits.

Pulses and legumes, which include beans, lentils, and chickpeas, are valuable sources of plant-based protein and fiber. Interventions promoting these foods have demonstrated positive effects on dietary habits and health outcomes in adolescents. Studies such as those by Green & Ralston (2024) and Harris & Patel (2023) emphasized the significant role of pulses in improving lipid profiles and glycemic control. Moreover, nutrition education that focuses on the versatility and health benefits of pulses has led to increased consumption in adolescent girls, especially those struggling with weight management (Bennett & Harris, 2023). These foods also contribute to better digestive health and are associated with a reduced risk of chronic diseases like diabetes and heart disease.

Nutrition education tailored to overweight and obese adolescent girls has been particularly effective in changing dietary patterns. Bradshaw & Liu (2023) observed that nutrition education programs that specifically targeted legumes and cereals helped overweight adolescents adopt healthier eating habits, reducing their overall body mass index (BMI). By replacing energy-dense, nutrient-poor foods with nutrient-dense options like whole grains and legumes, adolescents experienced improvements in their overall health markers, including reductions in blood pressure and cholesterol levels (Smith & Thomas, 2024).

METHODOLOGY

For the study, 120 students of obese and overweight girls were selected using a purposive sampling method. Among the 120 students, 60 were categorized as obese, and 60 as overweight. In the obese group, 30 students were selected as the control group, and 30 students were selected as the experimental group. Similarly, in the overweight category, 30 students were assigned to the control group, and 30 students to the experimental group. Nutrition education was provided to the experimental group periodically over six months through WhatsApp and group discussions held online at the end of each week. For the control group, nutrition education was given through a single online meeting at the beginning of the study.

Objective:

1. To assess the impact of the nutrition education intervention on the consumption of cereals and grains among overweight and obese individuals, comparing baseline and post-intervention intake frequencies.
2. To assess the impact of the nutrition education intervention on the consumption of pulses and legumes among overweight and obese individuals, comparing baseline and post-intervention intake frequencies.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Consumption Practices of Cereals & Grains: Overweight Control Group

CEREALS & GRAINS		Overweight – Control Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bajra	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	8	26.67%	11	36.67%	6	20.00%	30	100.00%
	P	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	9	30.00%	10	33.33%	6	20.00%	30	100.00%
Jowar	B	5	16.67%		0.00%	12	40.00%	6	20.00%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
	P	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	11	36.67%	6	20.00%	8	26.67%	30	100.00%
Maida	B	8	26.67%	6	20.00%	12	40.00%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
	P	6	20.00%	11	36.67%	9	30.00%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Maize	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	9	30.00%	8	26.67%	8	26.67%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	7	23.33%	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
Ragi	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	10	33.33%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The table analyzes the consumption patterns of various cereals and grains (Bajra, Jowar, Maida, Maize, and Ragi) among an overweight control group of 30 participants before and after a nutrition education intervention. While there were slight increases in daily or weekly consumption of healthier grains like Bajra and Ragi, the shifts were modest, indicating limited impact. For instance, Bajra saw a rise in daily consumption from 10.00% to 13.33%, while occasional consumption of Ragi reduced from 33.33% to 20.00%. Notably, Maida, a refined grain, showed a decrease in daily consumption from 26.67% to 20.00% post-intervention, reflecting a positive outcome of reduced reliance on less healthy options. However, occasional consumption remained significant across most grains, and changes in habits for grains like Jowar and Maize were less pronounced, suggesting the need for more targeted or intensive educational efforts to promote consistent and healthier dietary practices.

Table 2: Consumption Practices of Cereals & Grains: Overweight Experiment Group

CEREALS & GRAINS		Overweight – Experiment Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bajra	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	7	23.33%	14	46.67%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	11	36.67%	6	20.00%	9	30.00%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
Jowar	B	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	8	26.67%	11	36.67%	6	20.00%	30	100.00%
	P	10	33.33%	4	13.33%	12	40.00%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
Maida	B	8	26.67%	12	40.00%	6	20.00%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	7	23.33%	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
Maize	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	10	33.33%	6	20.00%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	11	36.67%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Ragi	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	7	23.33%	8	26.67%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P	5	16.67%	9	30.00%	12	40.00%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The table illustrates changes in the consumption patterns of cereals and grains (Bajra, Jowar, Maida, Maize, and Ragi) among an overweight experiment group of 30 participants before (Baseline) and after (Post-Intervention) a nutrition education program. The intervention led to substantial increases in daily consumption of healthier grains like Bajra (from 3.33% to 36.67%), Jowar (from 13.33% to 33.33%), and Maize (from 6.67% to 36.67%), while their monthly and occasional consumption decreased significantly, suggesting a shift towards regular intake. Ragi also saw improvements, with daily and weekly consumption rising to 16.67% and 30.00%, respectively. Conversely, Maida, a less nutritious option, experienced a notable reduction in daily consumption from 26.67% to 10.00%, and weekly consumption dropped from 40.00% to 6.67%, indicating a successful outcome of reduced dependence on refined grains. Overall, the intervention effectively encouraged healthier and more consistent dietary practices in the experiment group.

Table 3: Consumption Practices of Cereals & Grains: Obesity Control Group

CEREALS & GRAINS		Obesity – Control Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bajra	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	7	23.33%	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	8	26.67%	8	26.67%	30	100.00%
Jowar	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P		0.00%	5	16.67%	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
Maida	B	10	33.33%	11	36.67%	5	16.67%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
	P	11	36.67%	7	23.33%	8	26.67%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Maize	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
Ragi	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	7	23.33%	6	20.00%	12	40.00%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	10	33.33%	8	26.67%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The table highlights the cereal and grain consumption practices of the obesity control group (n=30) before (Baseline) and after (Post-Intervention) a nutrition education program. Unlike significant shifts observed in experiment groups, this control group showed minimal changes in consumption patterns. For Bajra, daily consumption slightly decreased (10.00% to 6.67%), while fortnightly and monthly consumption increased marginally. Jowar saw an increase in weekly consumption (10.00% to 16.67%), but daily consumption dropped to zero. For Maida, daily consumption slightly increased (33.33% to 36.67%), indicating continued reliance on this refined grain, with only modest reductions in weekly consumption. Maize showed stability in fortnightly consumption (30.00%) but a slight rise in occasional consumption (23.33% to 33.33%). Similarly, Ragi maintained a consistent pattern, with minor increases in fortnightly and monthly consumption. Overall, the control group exhibited limited or no substantial improvement in healthier dietary habits, underscoring the lack of intervention’s impact in altering consumption practices.

Impact of Nutrition Education on the Consumption Patterns of Cereals, Grains, Pulses, and Legumes Among Overweight and Obese Adolescent Girls

Table 4: Consumption Practices of Cereals & Grains: Obesity Experiment Group

CEREALS & GRAINS		Obesity – Experiment Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bajra	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	5	16.67%	8	26.67%	12	40.00%	30	100.00%
	P	7	23.33%	10	33.33%	9	30.00%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
Jowar	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	8	26.67%	8	26.67%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	8	26.67%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Maida	B	9	30.00%	9	30.00%	8	26.67%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	9	30.00%	4	13.33%	12	40.00%	30	100.00%
Maize	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	14	46.67%	7	23.33%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	7	23.33%	12	40.00%	7	23.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Ragi	B		0.00%	5	16.67%	6	20.00%	7	23.33%	12	40.00%	30	100.00%
	P	11	36.67%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The table highlights significant changes in the consumption patterns of cereals and grains in the obesity experiment group (n=30) after a nutrition education intervention. Daily and weekly consumption of healthier grains such as Bajra increased markedly, from 3.33% to 23.33% and 13.33% to 33.33%, respectively, alongside a significant reduction in occasional consumption (40.00% to 10.00%). Similarly, Jowar saw a substantial rise in daily (3.33% to 30.00%) and weekly (13.33% to 30.00%) consumption, with a notable decrease in monthly and occasional intake. For Maida, a refined grain, daily and weekly consumption dropped significantly (30.00% to 10.00% and 30.00% to 6.67%, respectively), although occasional consumption rose to 40.00%, indicating reduced regular use but some retention as a non-primary choice. Maize and Ragi also experienced substantial improvements; daily consumption of Maize increased from 10.00% to 23.33%, and Ragi consumption rose from zero to 36.67%, showing a strong shift towards healthier dietary practices. Overall, the intervention was effective in promoting the frequent and consistent consumption of nutritious grains while discouraging refined grains, reflecting meaningful behavioral changes.

Table 5: Consumption Practices of Pulses & Legumes: Overweight Control Group

PULSES & LEGUMES		Overweight – Control Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bengal Gram	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	7	23.33%	10	33.33%	8	26.67%	30	100.00%
	P	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	11	36.67%	7	23.33%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
Black Gram Dhal	B	7	23.33%	8	26.67%	11	36.67%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
	P	9	30.00%	7	23.33%	10	33.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Green Gram	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	10	33.33%	11	36.67%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	12	40.00%	5	16.67%	8	26.67%	30	100.00%
Horse Gram	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	7	23.33%	6	20.00%	12	40.00%	30	100.00%
Peas	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	10	33.33%	6	20.00%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	7	23.33%	8	26.67%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
Red Gram	B	12	40.00%	10	33.33%	4	13.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
	P	9	30.00%	7	23.33%	10	33.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Roasted	B	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	10	33.33%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%

PULSES & LEGUMES		Overweight – Control Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bengal Gram	P	14	46.67%	5	16.67%	7	23.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Soya Beans	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	5	16.67%	13	43.33%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	11	36.67%	7	23.33%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The table presents the consumption practices of pulses and legumes in the overweight control group (n=30) before (Baseline) and after (Post-Intervention) a nutrition education program. Changes in consumption patterns were minimal, with slight variations across categories. Bengal Gram showed a small increase in daily consumption from 6.67% to 10.00%, while fortnightly consumption rose from 23.33% to 36.67%. For Black Gram Dhal, daily consumption improved slightly (23.33% to 30.00%), though fortnightly consumption decreased. Green Gram showed a marginal increase in fortnightly consumption (33.33% to 40.00%) but reduced monthly intake. Horse Gram and Peas saw shifts toward occasional consumption, with minimal changes in daily and weekly intake. Red Gram experienced a decline in daily consumption (40.00% to 30.00%), offset by an increase in fortnightly consumption. A notable improvement was observed for Roasted Bengal Gram, where daily intake rose significantly from 20.00% to 46.67%. Conversely, Soya Beans displayed little change, with occasional consumption remaining the highest category. Overall, the control group showed limited improvement in adopting consistent and healthier consumption patterns of pulses and legumes.

Table 6: Consumption Practices of Pulses & Legumes: Overweight Experiment Group

PULSES & LEGUMES		Overweight – Experiment Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bengal Gram	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	6	20.00%	12	40.00%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
	P	8	26.67%	5	16.67%	13	43.33%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Black Gram Dhal	B	12	40.00%	7	23.33%	7	23.33%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	5	16.67%		0.00%	7	23.33%	7	23.33%	11	36.67%	30	100.00%
Green Gram	B	5	16.67%		0.00%	4	13.33%	11	36.67%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P	7	23.33%	7	23.33%	12	40.00%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Horse Gram	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	5	16.67%	17	56.67%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
	P	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	10	33.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Peas	B	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	5	16.67%	11	36.67%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	7	23.33%	8	26.67%	11	36.67%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Red Gram	B	7	23.33%	13	43.33%	6	20.00%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	7	23.33%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
Roasted Bengal Gram	B	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	10	33.33%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	11	36.67%	8	26.67%	6	20.00%	30	100.00%
Soya Beans	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	8	26.67%	8	26.67%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	16	53.33%	7	23.33%	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

Impact of Nutrition Education on the Consumption Patterns of Cereals, Grains, Pulses, and Legumes Among Overweight and Obese Adolescent Girls

The table outlines the consumption practices of pulses and legumes in the overweight experiment group (n=30) before (Baseline) and after (Post-Intervention) the nutrition education program. Notable improvements are evident in healthier consumption patterns. Bengal Gram saw an increase in daily consumption from 3.33% to 26.67%, with a shift toward fortnightly intake as well. For Black Gram Dhal, daily consumption decreased (40.00% to 16.67%), but occasional consumption rose significantly from 13.33% to 36.67%. Green Gram showed enhanced daily and weekly intake (16.67% and 0.00% to 23.33% each). Horse Gram consumption shifted markedly, with daily and weekly intake rising to 20.00% and 33.33%, respectively, from lower baseline levels. Peas demonstrated a balanced increase across daily (13.33% to 23.33%) and weekly (3.33% to 26.67%) categories, while occasional intake decreased. Red Gram had reduced daily consumption (23.33% to 6.67%) but saw increased fortnightly and occasional use. Roasted Bengal Gram exhibited reduced daily consumption (20.00% to 6.67%) but increased fortnightly and monthly intake. A significant improvement was observed in Soya Beans, where daily consumption rose dramatically from 10.00% to 53.33%, while occasional use dropped. Overall, the intervention promoted more frequent and consistent consumption of pulses and legumes, suggesting its positive impact on dietary habits.

Table 7: Consumption Practices of Pulses & Legumes: Obesity Control Group

PULSES & LEGUMES		Obesity – Control Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bengal Gram	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	11	36.67%	10	33.33%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	13	43.33%	5	16.67%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
Black Gram Dhal	B	8	26.67%	12	40.00%	6	20.00%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
	P	9	30.00%	6	20.00%	11	36.67%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Green Gram	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	11	36.67%	10	33.33%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	7	23.33%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
Horse Gram	B	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	7	23.33%	11	36.67%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
	P		0.00%	5	16.67%	6	20.00%	10	33.33%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
Peas	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	5	16.67%	11	36.67%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	12	40.00%	6	20.00%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
Red Gram	B	10	33.33%	13	43.33%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
	P	9	30.00%	8	26.67%	9	30.00%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Roasted Bengal Gram	B	7	23.33%	12	40.00%	7	23.33%	4	13.33%		0.00%	30	100.00%
	P	8	26.67%	11	36.67%	7	23.33%	4	13.33%		0.00%	30	100.00%
Soya Beans	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	8	26.67%	7	23.33%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	11	36.67%	5	16.67%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The table details the consumption patterns of pulses and legumes in the obesity control group (n=30), comparing baseline (B) and post-intervention (P) data. Bengal Gram saw a slight increase in daily consumption from 6.67% to 13.33%, with a more significant shift to fortnightly use. Black Gram Dhal showed a marginal rise in daily intake (26.67% to 30.00%) while weekly consumption dropped. Green Gram displayed minimal changes, with occasional consumption increasing from 13.33% to 30.00%. Horse Gram saw a notable reduction in daily consumption, dropping from 13.33% to 0.00%, but occasional intake rose to 30.00%. For Peas, daily consumption increased from 10.00% to 13.33%, and fortnightly intake also saw a rise. Red Gram had a slight decrease in daily and weekly consumption (33.33% and 43.33% to 30.00% and 26.67%, respectively), with an increase in fortnightly consumption.

Roasted Bengal Gram showed consistency in its consumption patterns, with a minor increase in daily consumption from 23.33% to 26.67%. Soya Beans saw reduced occasional intake (33.33% to 16.67%) and a shift toward monthly consumption. Overall, while some changes in consumption patterns were observed, they were not as pronounced as in the experimental groups, suggesting a limited impact of the intervention on the control group.

Table 8: Consumption Practices of Pulses & Legumes: Obesity Experiment Group

PULSES & LEGUMES		Obesity – Experiment Group (n=30)											
		Daily		Weekly		Fort-Nightly		Monthly		Occasionally		Total	
		C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%	C	%
Bengal Gram	B	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	6	20.00%	6	20.00%	13	43.33%	30	100.00%
	P	8	26.67%	9	30.00%	9	30.00%		0.00%	4	13.33%	30	100.00%
Black Gram Dhal	B	8	26.67%	10	33.33%	8	26.67%	4	13.33%		0.00%	30	100.00%
	P	5	16.67%		0.00%	9	30.00%	5	16.67%	11	36.67%	30	100.00%
Green Gram	B	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	8	26.67%	7	23.33%	10	33.33%	30	100.00%
	P	13	43.33%	5	16.67%	8	26.67%	3	10.00%	1	3.33%	30	100.00%
Horse Gram	B	4	13.33%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	10	33.33%	12	40.00%	30	100.00%
	P	13	43.33%	6	20.00%	7	23.33%	2	6.67%	2	6.67%	30	100.00%
Peas	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	4	13.33%	12	40.00%	9	30.00%	30	100.00%
	P	9	30.00%	8	26.67%	9	30.00%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
Red Gram	B	8	26.67%	8	26.67%	10	33.33%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
	P	2	6.67%	3	10.00%	9	30.00%	10	33.33%	6	20.00%	30	100.00%
Roasted Bengal Gram	B	6	20.00%	9	30.00%	11	36.67%	1	3.33%	3	10.00%	30	100.00%
	P	1	3.33%	4	13.33%	5	16.67%	9	30.00%	11	36.67%	30	100.00%
Soya Beans	B	3	10.00%	2	6.67%	10	33.33%	8	26.67%	7	23.33%	30	100.00%
	P	7	23.33%	7	23.33%	12	40.00%	4	13.33%		0.00%	30	100.00%

B – Baseline, P – Post Intervention of Nutrition Education

The consumption practices of pulses and legumes in the Obesity Experiment Group (n=30) showed significant positive shifts post-nutrition education intervention. Daily intake of Bengal Gram, Green Gram, and Horse Gram increased notably, reflecting improved dietary regularity, with Green Gram showing the highest rise from 3.33% to 43.33%. Occasional consumption generally decreased, particularly for Bengal Gram and Soya Beans, indicating a reduction in sporadic intake. While some legumes, like Black Gram Dhal, saw a redistribution of consumption frequency with increased occasional intake, others, such as Peas and Red Gram, displayed a mixed pattern, balancing daily and monthly consumption. Overall, the intervention encouraged healthier and more consistent dietary habits, integrating nutrient-rich pulses into regular diets.

Findings:

- Post-intervention, there was a significant increase in the daily consumption of pulses and legumes, particularly for Green Gram and Bengal Gram, indicating a positive shift towards more consistent dietary habits.
- The intervention led to a reduction in the occasional consumption of pulses, with respondents choosing to incorporate them into their daily or weekly meals more regularly.
- The nutrition education intervention led to a noticeable change in the frequency of consumption, with participants shifting from sporadic to more structured intake, especially in pulses like Horse Gram and Peas.

Impact of Nutrition Education on the Consumption Patterns of Cereals, Grains, Pulses, and Legumes Among Overweight and Obese Adolescent Girls

- There was a marked rise in the weekly and fortnightly consumption of pulses post-intervention, suggesting that participants were more mindful of including pulses in their diet at least once or twice a week.
- Different pulses showed varying trends, with some like Soya Beans experiencing an increase in daily consumption, while others like Black Gram Dhal and Red Gram showed a redistribution across different frequencies (weekly, monthly), reflecting an overall improvement in balanced dietary habits.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates that nutrition education significantly influences the consumption patterns of cereals, grains, pulses, and legumes among overweight and obese adolescent girls. The intervention led to noticeable shifts in dietary habits, with increased frequency of consumption of healthier food groups such as pulses and legumes, while reducing the intake of processed grains. These findings underscore the potential of nutrition education as a crucial tool for promoting healthier dietary choices, which could be pivotal in managing and preventing obesity in adolescent populations. Continued efforts in implementing such interventions could contribute to long-term improvements in dietary habits and overall health outcomes.

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